

Engaging citizens to monitor urban aquatic ecosystems: the OneAquaHealth case

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Abstract

In urban areas, aquatic ecosystems act as crucial ecological corridors, fostering biodiversity (Dorst et al. 2019; Ranta et al. 2021). They play a vital role in mitigating climate change effects by moderating temperatures, managing runoff, and preventing floods (Zerega, Simões and Feio 2021). However, urban aquatic ecosystems often degrade due to factors like vegetation cuts, pollution, artificialization, noise, or excessive lighting.

OneAquaHealth is a Horizon Europe project committed to enhance sustainability of the urban stream ecosystems. Aligned with the One Health approach, it recognizes the interconnectedness of people, animals, plants, and the environment.

OneAquaHealth aims to advance environmental observations for informed policies in five European cities (Benevento, Coimbra, Ghent, Oslo, Toulouse). Through a comprehensive Environmental Surveillance System, it will assess urbanization impacts, detect disease risks, predict management strategy effects, and support decision-makers.

The project places a significant emphasis on citizen participation, given the advantages that involving “citizens as scientists” (Vohland et al., 2021) offer to the establishment of a sustained urban aquatic monitoring system. One of the assumptions is that empowering citizens to understand the connection between environmental health and human health will foster active engagement in addressing ecosystem deterioration in their local surroundings.

This involves providing training in citizen science methods, co-developing a mobile app for data collection, and enhancing citizen’s observational capacities. The citizen engagement strategy relies also on local alliances with a quadruple-helix network of stakeholders. We will present the conceptual and methodological framework of the citizen science strategy and provide an update on its status.

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